

HISTORICAL FOUNDATIONS OF PHRASEOLOGISMS

Abdullayev Muhammad-Ali Ravshan o'g'li

researcher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8166600>

Annotation: the main focus of phrasaeologisms as a branch of linguistics is on the study of the nature of phraseologisms and their categorical signs, as well as the determination of the laws of application of phraseologisms in speech.

Keywords: linguistics, phraseology, phrase, history, phraseological unit, speech, sign, proverb, meaning, semantics.

Although the phraseological unit is very ancient in terms of the origin of the phraseological unit, the history of phraseological science spans several hundred years. In Russian linguistics, researchers with phraseological units have been engaged since the XVIII century. In Particular, M.V.Lomonosov had drawn up a plan for a dictionary of the Russian literary language, in which, in addition to words, "proverbs of the people (Russia)", "phrases" and "idiomatisms" should be expressed. By the 60s and 80s of the 20th century, phraseology had grown rapidly in Uzbek linguistics, as in foreign linguistics. The first researcher of the theory of phraseology is undoubtedly the schwetzar-French linguist Charles Balli (1865-1947). He had contributed word associations, i.e. special chapters researching phraseologisms, to his works "Stylistics ocherki" (1905) and "French Stylistics" (1909). He had distinguished the external and internal signs of phraseological associations from birbiri. According to his teaching, the structural features of such associations are considered external signs, and the semantic nature is considered its internal signs. Phraseology should be mainly concerned with the study of the semantic nature of phraseological associations, internal signs. Issues of study of phraseology of Turkic languages.

Phraseology (Jun. phrasis is an expression, phrase and ...logic) - 1) the branch of linguistics that examines the phraseological composition of a language in its current state and historical progress; 2) a set of phraseologisms in a particular language.

The main focus of phrasaeologisms as a branch of linguistics is on the study of the nature of phraseologisms and their categorical signs, as well as the determination of the laws of application of phraseologisms in speech. The most important problem of phrasaeologisms is to distinguish and distinguish phraseologisms from (i.e., not pre-prepared) vocabulary generated in speech, and, on this basis, identify signs of phraseologisms. Depending on certain discrepancies between idiomaphraseologisms, phraseological compounds and stable sentences (proverbs and matala, other phraseologisms equivalent to a sentence), many researchers understand phrasaeologisms in 2 different ways: narrow and broad. When it is understood in a broad sense, proverbs and sayings, stable sentences characteristic of folklore, some forms of communication (greeting, farewell sentences) are also included in the framework of phrasaeologisms. But this issue, that is, the issue of understanding phrasaeologisms in a broad sense, remains still controversial. The main tasks or issues of

phraseologisms are: to determine the consistency of phraseological content and, in this regard, to study the sign(lik) nature of phraseologism; to characterize the homonymy, synonymy, antonymy, polysemy and variant of phraseologisms; to identify the peculiarities of words and their specific meanings in the structure of phraseologisms; to clarify the relationship of phraseologisms with word categories; to determine their syntactic role; the study of the formation of new meanings of words in the structure of phraseological units and other phrasaeologisms develop principles of separation of phraseological units, methods for their study, classification and description in dictionaries.

Based on the specific, diverse methods developed in phrasaeologism, the phraseological composition of the language is diverse: it is classified according to structural-semantic, grammatical, task-methodological foundations. The principle of structural-semantic classification is fundamental. Phrasaeologisms as an independent branch of linguistics appeared in Russian linguistics in the 40s of the 20th century. To its initial formation, Russian scientists A. A. Potebnya, I. I. Sreznevsky, A. A. Based on the works of Shakhmatov, the issue of studying stable (stationary) vocabulary in a separate linguistic Department — phrasaeologism-in the educational-methodological literature of the 20 — 40s-Y.D.Polivanov, S. Abakumov, L. A. It was raised in the works of bulakhovsky. In western European and American Linguistics, phrasaeologism is not distinguished as a separate branch of linguistics. Research in the field of phraseology in Uzbek linguistics dates back to the 50s of the last century. To this day, phraseologisms have been studied in various respects (Sh.Rakhmatullayev, B.Yoldashev, A.Mamatov et al.), several dictionaries on phraseologism were compiled (Sh. Rakhmatullayev, M. Sadiqova), from which writers studied the phraseological composition of the works of Abdullah Qadiri, Abdullah Qahhor, Hamid Olimjon, Aydin, Said Ahmad. In the 70s and 80s, A Center for coordinating phraseological research and issuing special collections operated under SamDU.

Although the term " phraseology "is derived from the Greek word " phraseology " (phrasis – expression, oratory scroll), in turkiology the term originally served to represent different meanings. For example, the Turkish scholar Mirza Kosimbek (1802-1870), who lived in the 10th century, derived from the traditions of the time and used the word "phrase" in his work to mean "sentence", "sentence" (predlojenie), as in other pictorial grammars written in Russian.

And when it was said " phraseological conjunction", it understood large linguistic units from the word. As he describes verbs in Turkic languages, he interpreted language units such as grief-eating, incarnate, gussa-eating as "constituent verbs" ("sostavnie glagoli"). Azerbaijani linguists B.Shepherd and F.In his work "grammar of the Turkish language", oghazoda, reflecting on the sections of language science, used the word "idiotism", along with the terms "Semasiology", "Stylistics", in contrast to the term "idiomatism", which was in widespread use in linguistics at the time. In this work, the authors cite as an example units of idioms in Turkish, such as hooking, hooking, peeping, drinking water from the eyeball (sendin). In general, phraseology is considered one of the relatively young areas in Turkology, since its systematic study began only in the 40-50s of our century. Researchers studying the grammatical construction of Turkic languages have also given importance to the features of the use of compounds in speech that are not dissociated into parts(components). Considering that such compounds are functionally close to the word, some Turkologists considered them lexical vocabulary or lexical units (lexical associations), and included them in the scope of the

object of study of the fields of syntax or word making. Other researchers, however, considered such compounds to be lexicalized compounds or fist compounds with lexical meaning, and advanced the idea that they should be an independent object of study of linguistics, without regard to both syntax and word making. Also, in turkiology, the views that phraseological compounds are integral fragments of a sentence, which should be the object of study of lexicology or phraseology, began to surface as early as the 60s. The initiators of Turkic phraseology are undoubtedly S.K.Kenesboev et al.U.Are considered rahmatullaevs. Their research, which occurred in the second half of the 40s and the 50s, played a large role in the formation and development of Turkic phraseology. The candidate dissertations defended at this time also left a significant mark on the progress of Turkic phraseology.

References:

1. Sh.Rahmatullaev. O'zbek frazeologiyasining ba'zi masalalari, Toshkent, 1966.
2. Sh.Rahmatullaev. Nutqimiz ko'rki, Toshkent, 1970.
3. U.Tursunov va boshqalar. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili, Toshkent, 1992.
4. Hozirgi zamon o'zbek tili, Toshkent, 1957.
5. A.Mamatov. Frazeologizmlarning shakllanish asoslari, Toshkent, 1996.